

UTILIZING THE MONITORING TOOL OF STUDENTS, PARENTS AND ADVISERS AS INTEGRATED IN THE UNIFIED WEEKLY HOME LEARNING PLAN TEMPLATE

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Abstract: This action research sought to assist SHS students in monitoring their own learning tasks during the transition to the new normal education system. The study sought to ascertain the extent of output monitoring and to investigate the difficulties students encountered when submitting their weekly output. The study also sought to determine how the newly developed monitoring tool assisted students in overcoming these obstacles.

To comprehend the difficulties students encountered in monitoring the learner's submitted outputs, this study used a qualitative research method. The researchers utilized purposive and random sampling to select Grade 12 STEM 2 students and parents as participants. Data was gathered through interviews with ten students and ten parents, with questions focusing on the difficulties encountered during output submission and how the newly developed monitoring tool assisted in overcoming these difficulties. The rich and detailed responses provided by participants enabled the researchers to identify patterns and themes related to student difficulties.

During the pandemic, the researcher explored the difficulties students had in submitting their work for a distance learning program. Missing output, a lack of motivation, technical issues, difficulty understanding tasks, and personal issues were identified as challenges. According to some related studies, these difficulties contributed to poor performance and failure to meet deadlines. Furthermore, the researcher investigated the program's monitoring tool and discovered that all students and parents were aware of its existence and how it worked. Overall, the study emphasizes the importance of addressing the challenges that students face in distance learning programs, as well as the need for effective monitoring tools to ensure deadline compliance.

Keywords: Weekly Home Learning Plan (WHLP), monitoring, learning tasks, output monitoring, monitoring tool, lack of motivation, technical issues, difficulty understanding the tasks, personal issues, failure to meet deadlines, effective monitoring tool.

I. CONTEXT AND RATIONALE

The learning process must include a rigorous examination of the output of the learners. It helps instructors to assess how well their students are acquiring new information and provide guidance on how to improve their skills. Automating this process with monitoring tools makes it easier for teachers to track students' progress and identify areas where additional assistance may be required.

One of the primary benefits of monitoring systems is that they may provide real-time data on student performance, allowing teachers to identify struggling students and intervene before problems escalate. Monitoring tools, for example, can provide information regarding the amount of time students spend on activities or modules, the number of attempts they make on quizzes or assignments, and how successfully they meet learning objectives. This knowledge can aid teachers in adapting their instructional approaches to better meet the needs of certain pupils or groups of students.

Monitoring systems also provide students with immediate feedback on their performance, which encourages them to continue learning and develop their skills. Immediate, specific, and actionable input is more likely to be beneficial than delayed or unclear feedback. With the use of monitoring technologies, the process of providing feedback can be automated, allowing teachers to do so more swiftly.

Among the available monitoring, technologies are learning management systems (LMS), online assessments, and analytics software. The nature of the course, the objectives of the instructor, and the preferences of the students are just a few of the aspects that will impact the choice of tools.

As the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan is still in its second year of implementation, the previous action research of the proponent, titled "A Unified Weekly Home Learning Plan: A Collaborative WHLP Template of Senior High School Teachers Using Google Sheet," is still being implemented continuously for the School Year 2021-2022. This proposal would like to add a few features to its original template to maximize its utility in pandemic teaching settings. The addition of features to the Unified WHLP Template would address the problem of students failing to supervise their submitted work. The parents have been unable to monitor their children's performance, while the advisers have only been able to place checkmarks on the grid of the weekly monitoring form without certifying the specific performance of students in different subject areas.

As the proponent is an adviser herself, the thought of modifying the monitoring tool form of the previous one to help students be responsible for monitoring their own outputs after their parents have checked them at home or prior to output retrieval. It is recommended that the monitoring checklist be incorporated into the Unified WHLP in order to reduce paper consumption and to make all involved persons in the monitoring process be on the right track of gathering their own outputs.

If the students would be reminded right away of those missing outputs he or she submitted on the day of retrieval, the issues on missing a portion of output will be lessened. Thus, the proponent of this study would like to improve the monitoring process in the Senior High School continuously utilizing the Unified WHLP.

II. ACTION RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This action research aimed to help the SHS students to keep on track of their own submitted learning tasks without adversity in the new normal education. This study would like to explore the extent of output monitoring of the students. Specifically, upon implementing this innovation, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the challenges encountered by the students during the submission of their weekly output?
2. How did the newly developed monitoring tool help them overcome the difficulties they encountered?

III. PROPOSED INNOVATION, INTERVENTION AND STRATEGY

A monitoring tool will be the added feature of unified WHLP template. In this monitoring process, the people involved in this output tracking are the students, parents or guardian and the advisers. The parents or guardian would sign the area on the last end of their WHLP to counter check the checklist of their child on the accomplished output within the week. And during the output retrieval the advisers confirms the checked list of output submitted by signing too the other end of the template. It is important that monitoring methods be implemented to set high standards in terms of students' effort and achievement increased to continually challenge the learners in their academic performance. (Cotton, K.) Monitoring techniques can also support increased motivation and engagement among students, which is a significant advantage. Students are more likely to remain engaged and motivated to keep learning and improving when they receive regular feedback and praise for good performance. (Blackwel, et al 2014)

The image shows a screenshot of a 'QUARTER 4 - Weekly Home Learning Plan' for 'GRADE 12 ACADEMIC TRACK' for the school year 2021-2022. The subject is 'SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING AND MATHEMATICS (STEM)'. The table below details the learning tasks and monitoring interface.

Learning Competency	Learning Tasks	CHECKBOX TO LEARNING TASKS	
	Daily @7:00 - 8:00 AM	Student	Parent/Guardian
	Wake up, make up your bed, eat breakfast, and get ready for an awesome day!		
	Have a short exercise/meditation/bonding with family (every Monday, Wednesday and Friday)		
	THURSDAY @ 4:00 - 5:00 PM - Revisit all modules and check if all required tasks are done.		
	FRIDAY @9:00 - 12:00 NN		
	Parents/guardian submit the output at the retrieval stations on the schedule indicated		
	Parents/Learners get the submits weekly outputs or get the modules (if any). (Remaining hours after or before submission of output maybe used to do other Learning Tasks)		
WEEK 1 & 2			
APRIL 18 - 22, 25-29, 2022			
MONDAY			
WEEK 1 - A- Contemporary Arts from the Regions @ 1:00 - 3:00 PM			
Discusses local materials used in creating art.	Module 1 Lesson 1: Local Materials Used in Contemporary Arts What I Have Learned Part 1: Multiple Choice (1-5) Part 2: Short Answer Test (1-3) p. 11-12		

Figure 1. Interface of WHLP with monitoring tool on the right side.

IV. ACTION RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used a qualitative research approach to investigate and comprehend the difficulties students encountered in keeping track of their submitted outputs. The researchers were able to find patterns and themes relating to the difficulties the students faced thanks to the rich and thorough responses it provided on their experiences and perceptions.

The researchers utilized a purposive and a random sampling to select the participants. In a non-probability sampling strategy known as "purposeful sampling," participants of this study were chosen in accordance with a predetermined set of criteria, such as students under Grade 12 STEM 2 and their parents submitting the output within the last week of output submission for the end of the quarter 4. Purposive sampling aimed to choose a sample of participants with qualities or experiences that are relevant to the research this research study.

A. Participants

The participants of this action research were Grade 12 STEM 2 students, and parents through random sampling. These respondents were a key component of the study as they give the needed necessary information to get the outcomes that the researcher needed. Students, parents, and teachers all have unique perspectives and experiences related to the monitoring of student output, and gathering data from each group can provide a comprehensive understanding of the issue.

B. Data Gathering Methods

During the retrieval period dated July 13 to 15, 2022, the researchers started to interview 10 students and 10 parents randomly. The respondents were asked of the eight (8) chunks of queries out of the main research questions of this study: What are the challenges encountered by the students during the submission of their weekly output? And How did the newly developed monitoring tool helped them overcome the difficulties they encountered?

Instrument

The researcher chunked the idea of the main research questions into eight (8) open-ended questions. Here follows are the questions initiated for the interview:

1. How did you become aware of the monitoring strategy used to track output submission?
2. What challenges did you have when submitting your output?
3. How did the monitoring tool help you to overcome these challenges?
4. What feedback did you receive from your instructors regarding the quality of your outputs?
5. How did you use the monitoring tool to track the progress of your outputs?
6. What strategies did you use to ensure that your outputs were of the highest quality?
7. How did the monitoring tool help you to identify areas of improvement in your outputs?
8. What suggestions do you have for improving the monitoring tool?

The same questions were given to parents as being addressed and applicable to them.

C. Data Analysis Plan

A qualitative research method is used here to be able explore the responses of the students and parents towards the enlightenment of the research problem on the learner's submission of output where usually misplaced and did not match to the activities assigned for the week. Here, also includes the content analysis to analyze the qualitative data into its common themes and patterns. There were two main research questions where eight generated questions given during the interview were used.

The questions are about the challenges encountered by the students during the submission of their weekly output and the assistance given to the students with the aid of the new developed monitoring tool to overcome the difficulties they encountered during output submission. The content of the questions in the interview inquires about learner's challenges during output submission, their awareness on the monitoring strategy implemented, the aid of monitoring tool to the challenges they encountered, feedback they receive from the teachers about the quality of the output, usage of monitoring tool to track their progress in their output, strategies the students use to put their output in highest quality, identification to improve output submission and quality and respondents' suggestion to improve the monitoring tool.

Responses were obtained through the use of a semi-structured interview guide containing the eight indicated questions above during the last output retrieval schedule. The researcher ensured the utmost confidentiality of the information the respondents would provide. The researchers took notes on all the main key ideas of the data with verification of these notes from the respondents themselves. These write ups of responses were treated with content and thematic analysis approach to identify the patterns, themes and meanings of the data set.

V. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND REFLECTION

The researcher examined closely the data collected by familiarizing with its content, how the notes are being expressed, how it is transcribed and how the content related to the research problem. By generating initial codes such as its concepts, themes and patterns, the following results were obtained:

A. Challenges on Output Submission

What challenges did you have when submitting your output?

Missing output

Students and parents would always complain that the output for the specific week were all submitted yet there were still call ups and unlisted record of output presented. Student 1 said “*Ang alam ko po kasi nagsa-submit ako pero may mga pagkakataon na naka-lagay ang pangalan ko sa group chat sa listahan ng mga hindi nagsubmit*”. Most of the students have the same sentiments that submission was accomplished yet the record did not confirm their compliance.

Lack of Motivation

There is also reasons about procrastinating the activities due to many distractions at home such as using cellphones, playing online games and being with friends despite the pandemic situation. It is due to students poor time management that they always failed to use their time effectively to complete the assignment before the retrieval schedule. Student 8 noted “*Ang hirap po kasi na gumawa sa bahay kasi ay alam ko na nasa bahay lang ako e magagawa ko din yun mamaya hanggang sa yun mamaya ko inabot nan ang oras ng submission.*” Students without autonomous character may find procrastinating the tasks assigned to them. It is important that there should be interaction between intrinsic goal and autonomy-supportive context where individuals will be encouraged to have self-determination and promote autonomy in pursuit their daily goal that would be meaningful to them. (Vansteenkiste, et al 2004) The role of motivation in promoting students’ participation in school activities must be given attention. Disinterest in the task, not valuing weekly tasks and absence of self-efficacy may hamper students’ engagement to learning process. (Tuner, J.C. & Patrick, H. 2004)

Technical Issues

Since some of the resources were put in Google Drive to enrich the modules that the students have, they could not accomplish the tasks well because of the network signal and data shortage. Eight students reiterates this sentiments why they lack motivation in doing the weekly tasks that resulted to not submitting on time their assignments. As one of them states that “*ang hirap po gawin maam ng task kapag walang reference, minsan po ang module hindi namin maunawaan, minsan me modules na softcopy lang ang binigay kaya hindi kami makasagot kasi sa bahay mahina ang internet.*” Kamali & Bahrololoum (2017) found in their study that the technical issues on submitting learner’s task is the issue of the internet connection and computer. That is also the reason why they cannot properly format their documents or tasks into the right instructions to the task requirements.

Difficulty in Understanding the Tasks

Since the pandemic has brought all learners to different distance learning modality, students usually encounter difficulty in understanding the lessons and it results in poor performance on answering the tasks. It is not only that the lesson is hard to understand when there is no teachers around, it is also because some learners do not have enough time to read and comprehend their lesson because some of them are juggling multiple responsibilities at home and some deadlines of the other subjects. Due to this not having enough time, it makes the students hardly understand the lesson and difficult to accomplish some of the assigned tasks. (Xie, et. al., 2020) Some answers of the students and parents fall on this reason because of their poor comprehension to the long text given in the modules and their time is not really being managed well. As one of those who have same ideas expresses “*Ang hirap po minsan ng tasks dun sa module kaya minsan ginagawa ko na lang sya ayon sa kung anong gusto ko at pagkakaunawa ko sa binasa ko. Dahil po dito nakakapag-submit ako ng late na output at maling output.*”

Personal Issues

Some of the respondents also mentioned their personal issues in their family which became their reason why they missed submitting the output. It contributes to students' failure of school tasks submission on time. One of the students cried out that due to family problems and financial difficulties they were not able to finish on time the tasks and truly affect them to comprehending the lesson. Citing the words of a learner "*Hindi po ako maka-submit ng output dahil nasa malayo po ako at kinakailangan ko pong magtrabaho dahil nawalan ng trabaho ang nanay ko. Dahil dito hindi po ako nakakapunta weekly para mag-submit ng output.*" One parent affirms this stating that the pandemic affects their family relationship and financial status. Financial constraint contributes to difficulty in submitting the output. Some also stated about family problems where parents got separated and this issue becomes significant predictor of academic procrastination due to the stress and anxiety that the students experience at home. (Alkhaim et.al., 2019)

B. Monitoring Tool in the WHLP

Awareness on the Monitoring Tool

How did you become aware of the monitoring strategy used to track output submission?

All of the students and parents became aware of the orientation made by the adviser. They are aware that the monitoring tool is embedded in the WHLP where students and parents need to sign up once they accomplished the tasks on the specific objective of the lesson. Orientation of a specific activity is an essential aspect in understanding the roles and responsibilities of the involved persons as well as the objectives of the project. This is a critical component to improve the implemented project based on its success rate. Luthans (2015) found out that the teams who obtained clear understanding of their roles and responsibilities performed better and gained more satisfaction on their work. The orientation made in this project of monitoring tool to improve student's performance in accomplishing their weekly output helped the parents especially the students to establish common understanding on how to accomplish each lesson's objective written in the WHLP.

Monitoring Tool as an Aid to overcome the Challenges.

How did the monitoring tool help you to overcome these challenges?

Challenges such as difficulty in understanding the tasks and lack of motivation were resolved because of the implementing monitoring tool in the submission of their output. Since the WHLP has the feature of week number, learning tasks, learning objectives and parent's observation through signing the work accomplished of the students, it becomes an advantage to those who complied with the instruction. They were being guided on what tasks the students need to accomplish and those tasks they missed to comply. Students were given a track management of their own work through this, and parents were also guided to oversee the tasks of their child in every subject. It becomes a real-time monitoring on students' performance in terms of their accomplishment of weekly tasks. This also gave an idea to the teachers to adjust the given activities to better meet the needs of the students. As the student claimed that "*Ang tasks ay hindi pare-pareho, may mga tasks na mahirap gawin kaya talagang naiiwan ito tuwing mag-sa submit, pero dahil sa may guide ako ng WHLP may checklist dun na sa isang week kung ano lang at kung ano pa ang di ko nagagawa na task.*" Nevertheless, the monitoring tool becomes a guide to the learners and parents to track their own accomplishment and lets them manage their own time in completing the tasks based on its level of difficulty and easiness.

Feedbacks Received during Monitoring

What feedback did you receive from your instructors regarding the quality of your outputs?

The students only receive a completion remark for their tasks in each subject and the quality of their output is not closely monitored in terms of the content and context of each specific subject. This is because the adviser may only be responsible for a few subjects, while other subjects are taught by other teachers who are not present in the retrieval area.

Furthermore, the only quality of output that the adviser evaluates is the format, which includes checking if the subject code number and title, as well as the learning task number and title, are included in the written or performance tasks.

While completing tasks is important for students, the quality of the work is also crucial for their learning and growth. Students need to receive feedback on their understanding of the subject matter, the coherence and relevance of their work to the learning objectives, and the accuracy and validity of their conclusions.

Therefore, it is important for teachers to monitor not only the completion of tasks but also the quality of the output. This can be achieved by providing specific rubrics and evaluation criteria that assess the depth of learning and understanding, as well as providing feedback that highlights areas for improvement and growth.

Track of Progress of the Output

How did you use the monitoring tool to track the progress of your outputs?

The monitoring tool can become a checklist for students and parents to see if learning tasks have been completed. For parents, they can only see how their child has accomplished each subject task, but they may not always be able to check the content because the subject matter may be outside of their comprehension. Students, on the other hand, can track their task completion and the correctness of their output.

In addition, students can see their progress in terms of weekly output submission when teachers provide a list of students with incomplete or missing output during the week. This type of monitoring tool can be very helpful for both students and parents, as it provides a way to stay on top of their academic progress and ensure that tasks are being completed on time.

However, it is important to note that monitoring tools should not be the sole means of evaluating student progress. Teachers should also provide feedback and assessments that take into account the depth of learning and understanding of the subject matter, and not just completion of tasks.

Student's Strategies on Submitting Output with Highest Quality

What strategies did you use to ensure that your outputs were of the highest quality?

How did the monitoring tool help you to identify areas of improvement in your outputs?

The students prioritize **understanding the task** requirements before proceeding to answer the module. They carefully read the lesson to ensure that they can answer the task correctly. However, if there are times when they could not understand the task and lesson, they **gather information from the internet**, watch videos on YouTube, or message their subject teachers for clarification. This indicates that students are proactive in their learning and are willing to seek assistance and resources outside the given materials to ensure the highest quality of their output.

Moreover, students prepare themselves in answering the task by **organizing their thoughts and planning** how they would construct their ideas to ensure that their output would be coherent and logical as required by the task instructions. This shows that they have good critical thinking and analytical skills.

By **communicating with their subject teachers and seeking clarification**, students demonstrate their communication skills and ability to learn on their own. This highlights the importance of communication in learning and the value of being proactive in one's education.

With the aid of a monitoring tool for the completion of their work, learners receive reminders of the tasks they need to perform. Adviser feedback on the completion and format of the output serves as guidance for students to improve the quality of their weekly submissions. This feedback loop encourages continuous improvement and enhances students' ability to reflect on their work.

In general, the students' strategic tactics consisted of active participation in their own learning and a willingness to seek resources and support in order to ensure the highest possible quality of their work. Students can continuously improve their learning experience and the quality of their work by using a monitoring tool and obtaining instructor comments.

Voice of the Students for Monitoring Tool Improvement

What suggestions do you have for improving the monitoring tool?

Some suggestions were obtained from students and parents on improving the monitoring tool embedded in WHLP. It is recommended that the monitoring may provide more detailed feedback. Instead of only providing completion and formatting feedback, the monitoring tool can provide **more detailed feedback** on the quality of the output. It is suggested to have **remarks** for the parents and students to see every week as a reminder on what to improve the next submission schedule. It also recommends having the **score sheet** of each output to see if the learners work meets the quality of task required.

These suggestions are good to consider for a monitoring tool improvement. Thus, customization is important to allow the teachers customize the feedback and grading criteria to suit their specific needs and learning tasks instructions. Feedback must include the content, organization, and coherence of the output to better monitor the learner's progress on their learning performance. The researcher also sees the importance of providing analytics and insights on student's performance, such

as number of tasks completed, average grade and areas for improvement. This feature of monitoring tool if added, will help the teachers track students progress and identify areas where students need more support.

Though the suggestions are worth considering, the limitation of this study may not guarantee its realization for future use due to expected changes to happen for the next school year. Nevertheless, it is still important to consider all learning modalities in terms of monitoring the submission of students' output.

VI. ACTION RESEARCH WORK PLAN AND TIMELINE

ACTIVITY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY
1. Modified the Unified WHLP Template adding the monitoring feature					
2. Orient the SHS students through advisers with the aid of video tutorial on how to utilize the new WHLP					
3. Implementation of the project within the second semester of the current year.					
4. Survey on the challenges met by the students in Monitoring their output					
5. Conduct of the research problem number 2 to determine the extent of monitoring process after the proposed solution to the issue.					
6. Revise and finalize the action research proposal based on suggestions of the research committee.					
7. Monitor the implementation Monitoring System					
8. Harvest the data from the added feature of Unified WHLP the monitoring tool from the adviser.					
9. Analyze and compare the data to see the significant difference of output monitoring effectivity among the students, parents, and teachers.					
10. Submit the completed action research for checking and approval by the research committee.					

VII. COST ESTIMATES

ACTIVITY	RESOURCES NEEDED	AMOUNT (PhP)	SOURCE OF FUND
1. Printing of unified WHLP with monitoring tool	5 reams of A4 size bond papers	750.00 (personal printing for in-house reproduction of the WHLP)	MOOE/SEF
TOTAL	PhP 750.00		

VIII. PLANS FOR DISSEMINATION AND UTILIZATION

ACTIVITY	OBJECTIVE	PERSON INVOLVED	TIME FRAME	SOURCE OF FUND	EXPECTED OUTPUT
Submit the completed action research to the research committee.	Accept and acknowledge the paper.	District Research Committee	July 8, 2022	None	Accepted Completed Action Research
Publish the action research to any DepEd Recognized Research Publication	Share the findings of the study.	Research Publication Personnel	August – December 2022	Personal Fund	Published Action Research
Participate to various Research Forum	Present findings of the study in either oral, or poster presentation.	Research Organizations of different level	August - December 2022	Local Fund	Journalled Action research

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